

Novel features in the oxidation of dihydroxy benzenes by 2,6-dichloroquinone-4-chloro-imide in acetic acid and sodium acetate buffer medium

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Kinetics of oxidation of quinol, catechol and resorcinol by 2,6-dichloroquinone-4-chloro-imide (DCQCl) in $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH-NaOAc}$ system is reported. The kinetic features of *ortho* dihydroxy and *para* dihydroxy benzenes are similar. The reactions are zero order in oxidant at lower concentrations of oxidant (below 0.0005 M) and fractional order in substrate. At higher concentrations of oxidant, these two compounds exhibit first order in oxidant and fractional order in substrate leading to independence. Resorcinol exhibits different kinetic features : first order in oxidant at all concentrations and fractional order in substrate. The major products are coupling products under these conditions. Reactivity order is resorcinol > catechol > quinol. This result is novel. A mechanism is postulated to explain the observed order and a suitable rate law has been derived.

Kinetics of the oxidation of quinol by variety of oxidizing agents under acidic conditions have been investigated by using stopped flow techniques leading to the formation of quinone. Reports on the kinetics of oxidation of resorcinol and catechol are rather few except for a few photo-chemical and chemical oxidations¹⁻⁵. In continuation of our preliminary report on the oxidation of resorcinol by DCQCl⁶, this investigation deals exclusively with the kinetics of oxidation of *ortho*, *meta* and *para* dihydroxy benzenes in acetic acid-sodium acetate and acetic acid-sodium citrate buffers.

Results and discussion

Resorcinol : The oxidation of this compound has been studied by few workers⁷ and reported quinone as a sole product. In the literature of organic chemistry there is no possibility of formation of *meta* benzoquinone. Hence the quinone that they claimed is not *meta* benzoquinone but a quinone whose composition and structure have not been given. According to us, resorcinol upon oxidation yields a radical at ring carbon, identified by ESR studies. Hence coupling reaction is the main reaction in resorcinol oxidation. The kinetic results in the case of resorcinol are first order in oxidant and fractional order in substrate. The reactions are accelerated with increasing pH towards alkalinity. Sodium citrate buffers are much more effective in accelerating the reactions. Plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time are linear up to three half lives confirming first order dependence in oxidant. $\log k$ vs $\log [S]$ plots are linear with fractional slope. Increase in the concentration of acetic acid, decreases the rate. Rate increases with increase in concentration of sodium acetate

and sodium citrate.

The sequence of reactions is as follows :

As reported earlier⁸ DCQCl hydrolyses as follows :

The present discussion deals with the initial oxidation of resorcinol by HOCl, the first hydrolytic product. On this basis the reaction mechanism has been suggested,

This happens when the substrate is in excess. On the other hand when the oxidant is in excess, the stoichiometry

is 1 : 1, leading to the formation of trihydroxy benzene. This has been established by independent experiments that there is no further oxidation of trihydroxy benzene (hydroxy quinol)

Oxidation of quinol :

In the concentration range at $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ of oxidant or less, the reaction is zero order in oxidant as proven by linear x/t plots. The reactions are homogeneous till about 25% of the reaction. Hence the rates are computed by using initial percentages to avoid any competing complication due to precipitation at later stages of the reaction. At lower concentration of oxidant the order of substrate is fractional tending to become independent apparently at higher concentrations of oxidant. With increasing concentrations of sodium acetate the reactions are faster, indicating that the decrease in acidity favours the reaction. Increasing acetic acid component decreases the rate of reaction. Interestingly the order of oxidant changes to unity at higher concentrations of oxidant. This is proven by linear $\log(a-x)$ vs time plots at concentrations of oxidant at and beyond $0.0015 M$. This is established further from the plots of dx/dt vs $(a-x)$ where the straight line pass through origin indicating first order nature. Between $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $15 \times 10^{-4} M$ oxidant we find dual nature-zero order and first order indicating mixed order nature of reaction. When the order of oxidant is one, interestingly the order of substrate is zero. Sodium citrate also enhances the kinetic rate. All the experiments have been designed using acetic acid-sodium acetate or sodium citrate system. Where the major reaction is coupling process, the sequence of reactions is as follows :

Mechanism :

Rate law :

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore \text{Rate} &= k[c] \\ &= kK_2 [\text{HOCl}] [\text{Quinol}] \\ &= \frac{kK_2[\text{HOCl}]_T[\text{Quinol}]}{\{1 + K_2[\text{Quinol}]\}} \\ &= \frac{kK_2K_1[\text{DCQCl}] [\text{Quinol}]_T}{\{1 + K_2[\text{Quinol}]\} \{1 + K_2[\text{HOCl}]\}} \\ &= \frac{kK_2K_1[\text{DCQCl}] [\text{Quinol}]_T}{\{1 + K_2[\text{Quinol}]\} \left\{ \frac{1 + K_2[\text{HOCl}]}{\{1 + K_2[\text{Quinol}]\}} \right\}} \\ &= \frac{kK_2K_1[\text{DCQCl}] [\text{Quinol}]_T}{\{1 + K_2[\text{Quinol}]\} \left\{ \frac{1 + K_2[\text{Quinol}] + K_2[\text{HOCl}]_T}{\{1 + K_2[\text{Quinol}]\}} \right\}} \\ &= \frac{kK_2K_1[\text{DCQCl}] [\text{Quinol}]_T}{\{1 + K_2[\text{Quinol}] + K_2[\text{HOCl}]\}} \end{aligned}$$

Oxidation of catechol :

At $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ concentration of oxidant or less the reaction is zero order in oxidant established by linear x/t plots. At these concentrations the order of substrate is fractional. Even at higher concentrations of oxidant the order of substrate is fractional unlike in the case of quinol where zero

order dependence in the substrate is observed at higher concentrations of oxidant. The reactions are faster with increasing concentrations of sodium acetate. Increase of [acetic acid] decreases the rate of reaction indicating that it is dipole-dipole reaction. At higher concentrations of oxidant, the order of oxidant changes to unity confirmed by linear log ($a-x$) vs time plots at concentrations of oxidant at and beyond $15 \times 10^{-4} M$. This is established further from the plots of dx/dt vs ($a-x$) where the straight line passes through origin indicating first order nature. Between $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $15 \times 10^{-4} M$ oxidant we find dual nature indicating mixed order of reaction. When the order of oxidant is one, interestingly the order of substrate is zero. Sodium citrate also enhances the kinetic rate. All the experiments have been designed using acetic acid-sodium acetate or sodium citrate system, where the major reaction is coupling process.

The rate law is similar to that of quinol.

The relevant kinetic data for quinol and catechol are given below.

[Oxidant] = $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ [NaOAc] = 0.2 M		$k_0 [M s^{-1}]$
[Solvent] = 5% Aq. HOAc Temp. = 30°		
Variant	Concentration of variant	
Quinol	0.005 M	0.22×10^{-7}
	0.01 M	0.29×10^{-7}
	0.02 M	0.36×10^{-7}
Catechol	0.005 M	1.6×10^{-7}
	0.01 M	2.6×10^{-7}
	0.02 M	3.06×10^{-7}

[Oxidant] = $1.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ [NaOAc] = 0.2 M		$k_1 [s^{-1}]$
[Solvent] = 15% Aq. HOAc Temp. = 30°		
Variant	Concentration of variant	
Quinol	0.005 M	1.6×10^{-4}
	0.01 M	1.5×10^{-4}
	0.02 M	1.24×10^{-4}

(contd.)

Catechol	0.04 M	1.48×10^{-4}
	0.005 M	3.57×10^{-4}
	0.01 M	3.9×10^{-4}
	0.02 M	5.12×10^{-4}
	0.04 M	6.9×10^{-4}

Comparison of reactivity of resorcinol, quinol and catechol in coupling reactions :

[Oxidant] = $1.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ [NaOAc] = 0.2 M		$k_1 (s^{-1})$
[Substrate] = 0.005 M [Solvent] = Aq AcOH 15%, Temp. = 30°		
Substrate		
Resorcinol		0.7×10^{-3}
Catechol		0.357×10^{-3}
Quinol		0.16×10^{-3}

The order of reactivity in the coupling reactions is resorcinol > catechol > quinol. These facts can be rationalized by considering the three radical species that are formed in the sequence of reactions with the oxidant.

It is clear that the stability of the radical will be highest in case (1) as the position is aided by *para* and *ortho* hydroxyl groups. Case (2) is less stable compared to case (1) because the position is *para* to one hydroxyl and *meta* to another hydroxyl group. Case (3) is least stable as the position is *ortho* to one hydroxyl and *meta* to another hydroxyl group. Thus the rate of coupling reaction is determined by the stability of the radical species formed in the oxidation process.

Experimental

Materials : All the compounds used are of higher grade. The product identification has been done by the method of Miller using chromatographic analysis.

Kinetic method : The method used is iodometry for estimating the concentration of 2,6-dichloroquinone-4-chloro-imide at various intervals of time. This has been checked by spectrophotometry measuring the loss of concentration of DCQCl at wavelength 320 nm.

In the case of resorcinol and catechol the reaction is homogeneous till about three half lives of the reaction where as in quinol, the reaction is homogeneous till about 25% of the reaction. Hence titrimetry is used in case of quinol in

most of the experiments, where as spectrophotometry and titrimetry have been used due to homogeneity till about 75% of the reaction for resorcinol and catechol.

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